

INTERPRETATION OF THE NATION IN BEHBUDI'S JOURNALISM

Normurad Avazov

Associate professor of Alfraganus university, doctor of
philological sciences,

normurod.avazov.63@mail.ru

+99897-724-47-77

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13959320>

Abstract. The author reveals the issues of the journalistic skill of Mahmudhodja Behbudi. His choice of words, techniques of using folk methods will be shown. Also, the political, economic, spiritual and educational directions of the author Behbudi's journalism in the Turkestan region as the main part of his progressive activity are analyzed. At the same time, it is studied that one of the main issues is increasing the literacy of the local population, promoting knowledge and education in the Turkestan region.

Key words : Journalism, progressive; nation; country; science enlightenment; interpretation, negligence; problem; perspective, skill.

Annatsiya Muallif tomonidan Maxmudxo'ja Behbudiyning publitsistikasidagi mahorat masalalari ochib beriladi. Uning so'z tanlash, xalqona usullardan foydalanish usullari ko'rsatib beriladi. Shuningdek, muallif Behbudiyning publitsistikasining Turkiston o'lkasida siyosiy, iqtisodiy, ma'naviy va ma'rifiy yunalishlari taraqqiyparvar ijodining asosiy qismi sifatida tahlilga tortilgan. Ayni davrda Turkiston o'lkasida mahalliy xalqning savodini chiqarish, ilm va ma'rifatni targ'ib qilish asosiy masalalardan ekanligi o'rganildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Publitsistika, taraqqiyparvar; millat; o'lka; ilm; ma'rifat; talqin, g'aflat; muammo; istiqbol, mahorat.

Интерпретация нации в публицистике Бехбуди

Аннотация

Автор раскрывает вопросы журналистского мастерства Махмудходжи Бехбуди. Будет показан его выбор слов, приемы использования народных методов. Также анализируются политическое, экономическое, духовно-просветительское направления публицистики автора Бехбуди в Туркестанском крае как основная часть его прогрессивной деятельности. При этом изучено, что одним из главных вопросов является повышение грамотности местного населения, пропаганда знаний и просвещения в Туркестанском крае.

Ключевые слова: Журналистика, прогрессивная; нация; страна; наука; просвещение; интерпретация, небрежность; проблема; перспектива, умение.

Introduction

The influence of Behbudi's publicism is extremely great. It is well known that they reached the masses of the people, especially the intelligentsia. Behbudi seriously thinks about each article, clearly imagines who it is intended for and for what purpose it is being written. In the same place, we are obliged to talk about the artistic skills of the writer.

How does this skill manifest itself? Let's try to answer this question first. Let's pay attention to Behbudi's choice of titles. Many of Adib's articles attract one's attention from the title. In them, the goal and purpose that the writer wants to express is clearly visible. The title itself does not leave the reader indifferent. The most important aspects of the subject will be sealed in them: "Rights are taken, not given", "History and geography", "About national history", "The history of Turkistan is needed", "A nation in need", "Who will reform the nation", "Habits that eat away at us", "Our factor, our desire", "Criticism must be sorted", "The statement is true", "History of the Turkic people", "Turkistan", "Duma and Turkistan", "Autonomy of Turkistan", "Who will write our national history".

Importantly, Behbudi's personal attitude is openly expressed in many of them. "History and geography", "About national history", "The history of Turkistan is needed", "A nation in need" shows the author's affirmative action, approval, consent, "The people of Tarkhi Turki", "Turkistan", "Duma and Turkestan", "Autonomy of Turkestan" articles show the author's negative and opposing point of view. All this once again confirms the presence of the writer - publicist's intense reaction to the facts of reality, the intense tension of positive and negative emotions, and the "invitation" to freely and passionately express an opinion on an event or problem.

Methods

in the article Behbudi's Turkestan country and his independence topic in lighting his "Turkestan autonomy", "Kazakh to our relatives open letter", "The need nation" such as from his works used. also "Right is taken do not give", "To young people address" such as works too was studied.

In the article Behbudi's Turkestan in the country independence for in the struggle of the nation fate solution to do directed images interpretation light up to give for description, to compare methods applied.

Results

At this point, it is appropriate to talk about Behbudi's method of putting the issue on the agenda. A writer begins most of his work with a "prologue". With this, he prepares the interlocutor (journalist, reader) for the issue, helps him to focus on this issue. At the same time, he creates conditions and opportunities for others to perceive and understand the most important aspects of the problem he wants to talk about. It can be seen that this situation is openly emphasized in some articles. For example, in the article "Students need help", we read: "We cannot tell the introduction to every work."

In practice, this idea has found its full effect. Let's turn to some examples. "As far as I know, during the time of the old government, everything could be ordered and ordered. People's efforts to reform and develop their religion and national affairs were not allowed. Nothing could be done without a response and without a trace from the government" [1].

Behbudi's art of persuasion is one of the bright signs of a writer's skill. Each article is decorated with this art. Not only the choice of words in the statement, the logical flow of thought, the consistency, but also the facts and evidence presented, even the accuracy in the details of the events, the impartiality in the enumeration of the evidence and facts also ensure this trust. Let's take a look at the article "About national affairs in Samarkand": "There are a lot of jobs, but there are few people. With the help of the magazine "Hurriyat" number 20, two

people were invited from all the societies of the city uyezds in Samarkand province, to establish the "Provincial Society" of Samarkand, to discuss the issues written in this number 20 "Hurriyat", from this point of view to the mentioned people of uyezds and cities in the regions and were sent to the societies in several letters. On July 11 and 12 in Samarkand, please wait for the institutions of the assembly. Five of the Russians - ten people came. Even two representatives from the "Peasant Society" in Tashkent came twice. But not a single person from the cities of Jizzakh, Kattakorgan, Khojand and Oratepa of Samarkand region came to this meeting. However, vital issues for Turkestan were discussed at this meeting" [2]. Or, in the article "Bukhara Events", the details of the meeting with the emir, the description of the situation and scenery there, and even the details of the relationship between himself and the emir do not raise doubts [3], on the contrary, the reader is under the influence of the narrator of the events.

At this point, it seems appropriate to dwell on the volume of Behbudi's articles. Behbudi has no large-scale articles. The largest of them is no larger than 5-6 sheets of computer paper in current dimensions. Most of them are the size of two or three sheets of computer paper. This situation alone prompts us to think that the power of Behbudi's articles is seen in his conciseness, the conciseness and clarity of his thoughts.

Behbudi's journalistic articles have a feature that often stands out. It is a repetition of certain ideas or facts. He follows this path in places that are considered important. But these repetitions should not be interpreted as a weak aspect of the author's style, but rather by the consistency, priority, and stability of the author's worldview and goals. In addition, repetitions, regardless of whether they are related to facts or a line of thought, are used by the author to achieve his goal, that is, he considers them a means of conveying to his addressee. Let's refer to some examples to confirm our opinion: "If we Turkestans spend the money we spend on weddings and condolence on the path of science and religion, we will progress almost like Europeans, and we will gain prestige and prosperity in ourselves and in our religion. No, if we continue in our current state, we will have nothing but error and ignorance in religion and the world."

"Let's try to open schools and madrassas, establish community and joint-stock commercial offices, send students to Russia and Europe, Egypt and Istanbul . Hey Turkestan Muslims, brothers! Open your eyes, learn about the world by looking at magazines and newspapers" [4].

As can be seen from the cited examples, the intellectual repetitions are related to criticizing and getting rid of some vices that depend on our traditions on the way to achieving a common and serious goal, and at the same time are considered as fetters for the development of the nation.

In general, almost all repetitions are subordinated to the purpose of emphasizing and strengthening the author's opinion. Only in some cases, the aspects related to the writing style of these repetitions become noticeable.

If we approach Behbudi's work from this point of view, it is possible to understand that his literary heritage had a significant impact on the development of the Uzbek language at that time. As you can see, Behbudi always keeps his reader in front of his eyes when he writes every article. This student's career, worldview, level, level of knowledge will not be

overlooked. These circumstances serve to define the standards of the writer's choice of words. Therefore, it is not difficult to see that Behbudi chose different words in his articles written for different classes of society.

When it comes to the already known reality, we see that the writer is satisfied with extremely concise and short, blunt expressions. On the contrary, it can be observed to comment without melting when talking about a phenomenon or concept that is new or unfamiliar to the local population, the interlocutor, the reader. Let's give an example so that our opinion will not be dry: "Melkiy kredit - the name of the government has been opening small banks in most regions of Turkestan region for three days and the summary procedure is working. Three to four members are elected from two to three dahas of each district, i.e. vulus. Those members who borrow money from the people will be given a loan of twelve percent with eight or nine terms, i.e. one hundred soums for one year with twelve soums interest" [5]. Or, "In some areas of Turkestan, a tithes is considered to be four tanabs, and in some areas, six tanabs." But the present profit is calculated by the calculation of desyatin, i.e. six hundred sargins . A field of 400 sargins gives one and a half tons of grain. One dozen two thousand four hundred marhib are sarjindur" [6].

Naturally, Behbudi's skills are very clear in using the purely Uzbek word. He understands the power of words. That is why it is used very delicately in practice. This can be seen simply in the appeal representatives themselves. "Oy, dear compatriots" ("About national affairs in Samarkand"), "Oy hazrat ulama va agniyo" ("Rights are taken, not given"), "Dear brothers" ("Unity is needed").

Behbudi can try to find words that will touch the hearts of the people who are of the same mind as he is addressing. These features are visible in our examples above. However, if we quote one more example from the above, it will not be superfluous: "Fathers! Know that autonomy has been declared for all peoples in Turkestan, and you know that a fee is charged, but not given."

use of the word "Bovurim" here can be considered as an artistic discovery. Only a person who understood and appreciated the people's psyche, consciousness, customs, national traditions and values could find this form of address. Such a great person is visible in the figure of Behbudi.

The sweetness and impressiveness of the Behbudi language is explained by its closeness to the folk language, or rather, the way of speaking. Behbudi speaks the vernacular. That is why folk expressions, proverbs, and proverbs are often visible in his articles. Probably under the influence of this spirit, some of Behbudi's sayings rise to the level of wisdom and proverbs. Folk proverbs embedded in the text of Behbudi's works stand out with a new brilliance. It is known that the proverb "If the child does not cry, the mother does not give milk" is usually used in situations where the need is strong.

Let's pay attention to another article. The popular proverb "Stretch your feet to the ground" encourages to refrain from unwanted actions or to follow social and moral standards in actions and activities. The pareniological unit also carries a methodological meaning in Behbudi's article: " Jews, Armenians, and others become state because of the bank . As for us, we will lose our property and reputation. For example, we don't stretch our legs towards our blanket" [7].

As a connoisseur of several languages, Behbudi also used subtle sayings, wise words, and folk proverbs that exist in those languages: "One should learn from the scholars and merchants of the Caucasus and Tatarstan:

A person is not given an effort until he makes an effort" [8].

Apparently, the proverb here is the same as the existing forms in Arabic and Persian languages. In general, Behbudi created a series of wise words as a result of the influence of such wise words and his personal observations. Examples such as "Rights are taken, not given", "Moziy is the scale of prospects" can be proof of our opinion. Behbudi's closeness to the language also allows for the use of its dialect materials, albeit occasionally. Maybe it just happens naturally. In any case, some elements specific to the Samarkand dialect show themselves in the proverbs: "They have societies in every city", "military organization" - "meeting of a military organization". Yainki is called "Soviet Left Datsky Rabochy Deputy", "Meeting of Soldiers' and Workers' Deputies" ("Union is needed", "Hurriyat", 1917).

Therefore, Behbudi consciously uses those elements to say "the language of the people" in his articles.

CONCLUSION

The completion of Behbudi articles is also unique. In this respect, we can talk about Behbudi's skill school. In some articles, the purpose of the article is directly related to the conclusion. The author puts it at the end of the article in order to understand the purpose correctly and fully. For example, the article "About national affairs in Samarkand" ends like this: "Our goal is to prepare the people for the founder of the assembly of representatives of city dumas and field zemstvos, and to send one or two people to our central council in Tashkent so that they can always work for the benefit of the people. to make it happen, to explain and to state that it is necessary to help a good government" [9].

Some articles end with "additional evidence". Wise words, folk proverbs or instructive thoughts of famous people perform this task. For example, "the founder's meeting is not given to us, but if we take it ourselves, because the fee is charged, not given" [10].

This excerpt is taken from the article "Revenue is taken, not given." Or in the article "Education Month" we see the following conclusion: "Moziy is the scale of perspective."

References:

- 1.Behbudi M. An impartial tribute to the honorable people of Samarkand. Hurriyat. - Samarkand, May 19, 1912
- 2.Behbudi M. About national affairs in Samarkand. Hurriyat. - Samarkand, July 28, 1917.
- 3.Behbudi M. Bukhara events. Hurriyat. - Samarkand, May 1, 1917.
- 4.Behbudi M. Address to Turkestans. Mirror. - Tashkent, 1914. - #27.
- 5.Behbudi M. Small debt. Mirror. - Tashkent, 1914. - #1.
- 6.Behbudi M. Grain, soldiers, land and military compensation. The voice of the workers. - Samarkand, August 2, 1918.
- 7.Behbudi M. Oh, the banks failed us. Mirror. - Samarkand, 1914. - #19.
- 8.Behbudi M. Fees are taken, not given. Hurriyat. - Samarkand, July 13, 1917.
- 9.Behbudi M. About national affairs in Samarkand. Hurriyat. - Samarkand, July 28, 1917.
- 10.Behbudi M. About national affairs in Samarkand. Hurriyat. - Samarkand, July 17, 1917.

